

Promising cultivars with resistance to gall midge (GM) in Kerala, India

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A severe GM outbreak in Kuttanad, Kerala, caused damage that exceeded 50% in many varieties during the 1990 wet season (Apr–May to Aug–Sep).

We evaluated 53 breeding lines from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, for GM resistance under natural conditions. Checks were susceptible Jaya and resistant Mahaveera. Each entry was planted in 5- × 2-m plots laid out in randomized block design with three replications.

Damage ranged from 0 to 58%. Damage severity in Mahaveera was 40%. Pest infestation was scored at 40 d after transplanting using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). Eleven entries were highly resistant (score 0 to

Reaction of rice cultivars to gall midge incidence in Kerala, India.

IET no.	Parentage	Incidence of gall midge		Grain yield (t/ha)
		Score (0–9 scale)	Silvershoot (%)	
10774	Sona/W1263	3	5.0	5.2
11515	IET5656/RP1579	0	0.0	6.4
12169	CB11/Ratna	3	1.4	4.9
12170	Ash/Kranti	0	0.0	4.5
12183	ARC5723/ARC6650/RP1579-38	3	2.6	5.6
12185	Swarnadhan/ARC6650	1	0.8	4.7
12186	IR50/Phalguna	0	0.0	7.1
12187	IR50/Phalguna	0	0.0	6.7
12188	IR50/Phalguna	0	0.0	3.8
12189	Ratna/ARC10654	3	1.0	6.8
12193	Ratna/IET6858	0	0.0	5.1
12795	Rajendra/ARC6650	5	13.4	5.0
12799	Phalguna/IR50	0	0.0	6.0
12800	Phalguna/IR36	3	1.0	7.8
12804	IET6858/ARC6172	0	0.0	4.8
12806	IR50/Phalguna	0	0.0	6.2
12808	Prasanna/IET5688	3	1.5	5.8
12809	Manasarovar/ET6187	5	7.3	3.4
12814	SYE75/IR28	0	0.0	4.6
	Suraksha	5	13.5	3.9
	Mahaveera	7	40.0	2.8
	Jaya	9	53.0	2.6
	LSD		12.6	

1), 6 resistant (score 3), 3 moderately resistant (score 3, and 3 1 susceptible

(score 7). Jaya showed a high incidence (score 9) (see table). □

Virulence of brown planthopper (BPH) in Raipur, India

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BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* is becoming a major rice pest in Chhattisgarh region in MP. To determine BPH virulence in the area, we evaluated BPH resistance in

Table 1. Resistance of selected donors to the BPH-population in Raipur, MP, India, 1989-90.^a

Donor	BPH gene	Damage		Honeydew in 24 h (mm ² /female)
		Score	Rating ^a	
Balamawee	<i>Bph 9</i>	4.1	MR	12.61
Swarnalata	<i>bph 6</i>	0.5	R	18.66
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph 3</i>	5.0	MR	31.51
Mudgo	<i>Bph 1</i>	9.0	S	78.89
ASD7	<i>bph2</i>	9.0	S	132.37
PTB33	R check	1.6	R	6.80
TN1	S check	9.0	S	66.34
ARC10550	<i>bph5</i>	0.8	R	10.10
Babawee	<i>bph4</i>	7.7	S	19.20
TN1		9.0	S	32.37

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Reaction of DRP^a Hyderabad, and Pattambi donors of resistance to the Raipur BPH population.

Donor	Plant damage		Donor	Plant damage	
	Score	Rating ^b		Score	Rating ^b
	<i>Hyderabad</i>			<i>Pattambi</i>	
Andrewsali	5.29	S	KAU8754	6.6	S
ARC 10660	2.28	R	KAU8755	8.5	S
ARC11321	2.32	R	KAU8756	7.22	S
ARC6632	3.84	MR	KAU8770	4.41	MR
ARC10654	3.17	MR	MO 5	2.11	R
ARC5981	1.77	R	Jyoti	0.68	R
ARC6172	1.16	R	Rashmi	2.08	R
Majila	2.65	R	Bharthi	6.17	S
ARC6601	1.74	R	KAU8772	4.40	MR
ARC5780 (b)	1.88	R	KAU25331	7.96	S
ARC6610	1.85	R	KAU25333	5.92	S
ARC5984	1.94	R	BR51	2.57	R
ARC6650	1.03	R	Pavizam	4.24	MR
ARC10550	1.01	R	Triveni	5.3	S
Velluthacheera	1.41	R	KAU1727	9.0	S
Manoharsali	1.35	R	PTB33 (R check)	0.92	R
Soinphul	1.97	R			
PTB33 (R check)	2.61	R			

^aDRR = Directorate Rice Research, Hyderabad. AP. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

donors from Hyderabad (Andhra Pradesh), Pattambi (Kerala), and IRRI, Philippines during 1989–90.

The standard seedling test showed Mudgo (*Bph 1*), ASD7 (*bph 2*), and Babawee (*bph 4*) to be highly susceptible; Rathu Heenati (*Bph 3*) and Balamawee (*Bph 9*), moderately

resistant; and Swarnalata (*bph 6*) and ARC10550 (*bph 5*), resistant (Table 1). BPH honeydew excretion test confirmed the results.

Hyderabad donors were also resistant in Raipur, indicating similar virulency patterns at both locations (Table 2). Of the 15 donors from Pattambi, 8 were